

Effects of Advanced Trauma Life Support® Training Compared to Standard Care on Mortality and Functional Outcomes in Adult Trauma Patients

Summary

Project Acronym

TERN

Project Number

Not applicable

Provide a dataset summary

The project codebook will comprehensively document metadata such as encompassing variable definitions, data collection procedures, and valid value ranges. A pilot study for this study estimates that approximately 75 variables per patient will be collected. Sample size calculations indicate a total of 6500-7000 patients to be included. The accumulated data is anticipated to remain below 500 MB in size, consisting exclusively of tabular text data. Data storage and will be facilitated through a secure database with API access, as well as archival and processing of .csv files on secure servers.

The codebook will be made available in a data sharing repository (e.g., GitHub or Zenodo), connected to a unique DOI. Upon the publication of the primary research findings, an anonymized version of the dataset will be released under the same DOI as the metadata. The data will be shared under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

FAIR data and resources

1. Making data findable

The metadata, comprising the comprehensive project-wide codebook, will be stored in a GitHub repository, enabling access to the version history. This GitHub repository will be linked to a Zenodo release, which will be assigned a persistent DOI. The same DOI will be used for publication of the anonymised dataset. By uploading comprehensive metadata to a searchable resource (a data repository), as well as having a persistent identifier assigned to it by the repository we make the data findable.

2. Making data openly accessible

The metadata, including version history, will be readily available as outlined and accessible from the start of data collection. To safeguard participant integrity, individual patient-level data will remain inaccessible until the project's completion. Upon the conclusion of the project and concurrent with the main project publication, an anonymized version of the dataset will be released under the same persistent DOI as the published metadata. Hence, our data and metadata will be accessible since a persistent identifier assigned by the repository will lead to them.

All data will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

3. Making data interoperable

No specific metadata vocabulary will be used. However, we will use standard vocabulary and keywords that are commonly used in clinical and injury research as much as possible. This includes for example the collection of injuries that will be categorised using ICD-10.

4. Increase data reuse

The metadata and anonymized dataset will be made openly available for reuse. In compliance with Swedish law, all research data will be archived at KI for a minimum duration of 10 years following the project's completion. We plan to make our data reusable by assuring high data quality and providing detailed documentation and metadata to support correct interpretation. Licensing will be clearly outlined in the repository when accessing the data.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

Data collection will be conducted by trained on-site project officers, specifically employed for this task. They will gather data as defined in the codebook. Due to the environmental constraints of data collection sites, the primary mode of data collection will be paper-based. Each patient will be assigned a unique patient ID. Paper-based data will be stored in accordance with local regulations at each site. An electronic data collection tool will be used to upload the data, with each site having its own unique URL.

The data collection tool is accessible exclusively via VPN with two-factor authentication. Data backups will occur at least every 24 hours. Long-term data storage will take place on KI servers in Sweden. All data transfers between servers will be conducted through encrypted VPN solutions. Remote work with non-anonymized data will require VPN access and two-factor authentication. Data will remain on project servers for analysis and will not be transferred elsewhere. Access permissions can be granted exclusively by the project PI or authorized delegates appointed by the project PI.